

A probabilistic novelty detection framework for data stream classification

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Abstract

In the last years considerable research effort has been put on modelling the ever growing data in streaming environments. Some of these efforts are related with streaming novelty detection. In this scenario, new classes may emerge, disappear, or drift within time while others are normally classified. Recent works model these events with non-parametric approaches, such as with an ensemble of classifiers that are eventually renewed to keep the model updated throughout the stream.

In this work, we tackle this scenario from parametric families based on probability distributions. The classes are assumed to follow a certain probabilistic family and the newcomer instances from new emerging classes are naturally assumed to belong to the same probabilistic family but with different parameters. In order to illustrate this general framework, a mixture of multivariate Gaussian distributions is used. The experiments have been run considering the control of which classes (known or new) arrive at each iteration of the stream, and how they appear in the feature space. It is shown that when the assumptions of the probabilistic model are fulfilled, this method outperforms literature non-parametric approaches.

1 Introduction

With the burgeoning of the Internet of Things (IoT), a lot of sensor data is available creating new demanding problems. Many of these problems have a temporal nature and evolve during time. For instance, in agriculture, plants are constantly monitored with a large variety of sensors. These sensors gather information about the moisture, air pressure and temperature, among others. The plants can be affected by some well known plagues. However, in some situations, a certain plague can change (drift), can be eradicated (disappear) and a new one can be discovered (emerge). Similarly, in mechanical engineering, a machine can be faulty for a variety of reasons. In some situations, these reasons are known and controlled. However, new types of faults can occur (emerge); the known ones can be definitely fixed (disappear) and also, the source of the known faults can change (drift). This evolving learning scenario is known in the literature as streaming novelty detection or evolving classes [10, 15, 17, 18].

This learning scenario can be seen as a combination of different learning scenarios such as *stream classification*, *novelty detection*, and *supervised classification*. In *streaming classification* learning scenario, the instances arrive either in batches or one by one, and not necessarily in equal time intervals. The aim is to classify these instances considering that some changes may occur during the stream. The so called concept drift. Therefore, the model needs to adapt to those changes in order to give accurate predictions [8]. In static *novelty detection*, also known as one-class classification [2, 12, 19], the problem consists on discarding the observations that do not follow a given (learned) pattern. Briefly, given a fully labeled dataset, a model is learned. At prediction stage, instances are checked whether they are similar to the learned model or not. If the instances follow a similar pattern, they are considered to belong to the learned classes. Otherwise, they are predicted as novel. However, in this learning scenario the appearance, disappearance or concept-drift of classes is not modeled. Finally in *supervised classification*, a fully-labeled dataset is given to learn the prediction model. New unseen instances arrive, and the model predicts its label [16]. In this case, note that difficulties like unbalance learning can occur [11, 3].

Streaming novelty detection techniques must be aware of all the problems that already face the aforementioned learning scenarios. Therefore, this is a challenging task with many research and application possibilities. The streaming novelty detection learning scenario can be seen in three different phases that are clearly distinguished. Firstly, in the *offline phase* a model is learned from a supervised dataset. Secondly, in the *online phase*, instances arrive in a stream fashion. For each instance, the model predicts its label. Once in a while, an instance is not similar to the already known model and hence, it is stored in a buffer. These buffered instances are known as new class candidates, or novelty pattern candidates in the literature [18]. When this fixed length buffer is full, the *update process* is run in order to discover new classes among the buffered set of instances. The predictions for the buffered instances are then output. In some literature works, the possibility that some buffered instances are outliers is considered. Consequently, the *update process* discovers novelty patterns and, at the same time, it filters outliers [20].

In this paper, a probabilistic framework that deals with streaming novelty detection is proposed. The data is assumed to be generated by a certain probabilistic model [16]. Hence, the newcomer novel classes are naturally assumed to belong to the same distribution family, but with different parameters. In order to deal with the concept drift, a multioutput regressor is used to predict the weights of the current model with respect to the buffered instances. In order to illustrate this general probabilistic framework, a mixture approach based on Gaussian distribution family has been adopted. Furthermore, a detailed experimental study has been carried out in which many aspects that were not considered in the state of the art are analyzed. For instance, the moment in which the new classes emerge is controlled. The number of new emerging classes that emerge at the same time. The rate in which these new classes arrive, as well as the rate in which the classes disappear. The overlap between the newcomer classes and the existing ones is also defined. And finally, the shape of the classes

is also modelled.

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed framework, a set of experiments have been carried out with both real and synthetic datasets. Concretely, the KDDCup 99 and the cover forest datasets have been used. Regarding the synthetic datasets, the SENCData dataset [17] has been used. Furthermore, another 5 scenarios have been artificially created that model different situations of overlapping and shapes. These scenarios try to cover a large variety of real world situations. In order to model the arrival of the classes, 6 strategies have been created. This strategies model the arrival rates by means of exponential functions. Hence, there is a fine control of which new or known classes are arriving at a time and if the arriving is abrupt or gradual.

The experimental results have been compared with two literature techniques, such as, MINAS [4] and SENC Forest [17]. The results show that when the data fulfills the assumed distribution family, the proposed framework outperforms the state of the art approaches, not only being more efficient but also more accurate.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 deals with the recent work in the streaming novelty detection learning scenario. Section 4 refers to our new methodological approach. In Section 3, the problem is formalized. In Section 5, the experimental results are discussed. Finally, in Section 6, the conclusions are exposed.

2 Related work

The streaming novelty detection has been seldom studied in the literature. However, an increasing trend can be found in the last 10 years [8]. This work is related to three learning scenarios: *stream classification*, *novelty detection* and *supervised classification*. Regarding the first topic, many works can be found in the literature that deal with streaming environments. These approaches can be divided into two main groups. On the one hand, the single model classification, in which only one model is used to classify the entire stream [9]. On the other hand, the ensemble classification, which is based on a variety of base classifiers has been used in the literature. This technique predicts the label of the newcomer instances by combining the predictions of each of the base classifiers.

Besides, in *stream classification* learning scenario the concept-drift is a challenging problem. Briefly, concept drift stands for a change in the joint probability distribution of the labels and the features, from one certain time to another. However, the source of these changes may vary and hence, some research has been carried out [6, 13]. Formally, data is generated by a generative mechanism \mathcal{G} that follows a certain probability distribution $p(X, C)$, the concept drift can be defined as: $\exists i : p_{i+1}(X, C) \neq p_i(X, C)$, where p_i stands for the joint probability distribution at time i between the features X and class C . This can occur due to a variety of reasons, graphically shown in Figure 1, that are known in the literature as follows:

- *Real concept drift* refers to the changes in $p(C|X)$. The changes can happen either with or without a change in $p(X)$.

Figure 1: Different types of concept drift [6].

Figure 2: Differences between class incremental learning and streaming novelty detection learning scenarios.

- *Population drift* refers to changes in the population from which the future samples will be drawn.
- *Virtual drift* happens when the distribution of the incoming data changes $p(X)$ without affecting to $p(C|X)$. In other words, the classification boundary is not affected even when the $p(X)$ changes.

Considering, *novelty detection*, a labeled dataset in which only one class is available is used to learn a model. At prediction stage, the newcomer instances are checked to belong to the learned model. If not, they are rejected. In essence, this learning scenario only accepts or rejects instances according to a learned pattern. However, it is not considered that the rejected instances are sufficiently cohesioned to form a new class. They are just classified as novel with respect to the already known classes [2].

Another similar learning scenario is the class incremental learning (CI-L) [7]. In CI-L supervised observations arrive, forming a supervised data stream $DS = \{(\mathbf{x}_1, c_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, c_n)\}$, with input features as \mathbf{x}_i and its corresponding labels as c_i . The task is to incrementally update a model $\hat{M} \approx P(c|X)$ from the newcomer data given a supervised data stream. In order to do that, batch of instances are available for the model, without taking into account the temporal order of the instances (if any). In other words, the task in this learning scenario is to infer a reliable model from the supervised data. This learning scenario is

different to streaming novelty detection since in the later, the model is updated without labeled instances. Moreover, the decision boundaries generated by both CI-L and streaming novelty detection, are notably different. On the one hand, the CI-L fully partitions the feature space; each split corresponds to a class. On the other hand, the streaming novelty detection scenario only bounds the minimum space in order to classify a class. Leaving unbounded space in which new classes might appear. These differences can be graphically seen in Figure 2.

In streaming novelty detection, the aforementioned learning scenarios are combined [4, 15, 14, 18, 17, 10]. The classes are supposed to be born (emerge), change (drift), reborn and disappear. Two interesting situations occur in this learning scenario. On the one hand, the problem naturally becomes in a dynamically imbalanced learning scenario [21] whenever a new class emerges. On the other hand, at the offline phase, a fully labeled dataset is supplied to learn the initial model. Hence, the problem starts from a supervised classification paradigm. However, as the stream flows, unsupervised data arrives and this data changes the supervised models that were initially learned. Therefore, it can be said that the problem gradually transitions from supervised to unsupervised classification paradigm. Apparently, this might not suppose a difficulty, but the confidence of the predictions might not be reliable due to the absence of ground truth at some point of the stream.

Regarding the techniques that have been used in the literature to deal with streaming novelty detection, a variety of approaches can be found. For instance in [14, 15], an ensemble of classifiers is learned. Each classifier consists on a variety of spherical clusters conformed by a center and a radius. Each class is represented by more than one cluster. When a new instance arrives, it is checked whether it is inside the decision boundary formed by the union of the outlines of the spherical clusters, or not. If for all the classifiers of the ensemble, the instance is outside any decision boundary of known classes, it is considered as candidate to form a new class and it is stored in a buffer (see Figure 3). The discovering process of new classes is done under the assumption of cohesion and separation with an adapted version of silhouette coefficient. In [4], k-means or clustream clustering algorithms are used to model the existing classes. Similar to [15], a class is represented by a large variety of individual micro-clusters. However, different events are considered whenever a novelty pattern is found, such that the new micro-clusters are not valid and hence, the former instances are output as outliers; the new micro-clusters are an extension of a known class, modeling the concept-drift; or that the new micro-clusters form a new class. In [18] and [17], the new class is discovered using an ensemble of isolation forests, while the classification among existing classes is done using a random forest classifier. In [10], at prediction stage, semi-supervised chunks are provided to the algorithm. In this way, the confidence of the novel class existence is reinforced. In order to discover new classes, similar to [15], spherical decision boundaries are learned from known classes.

As can be seen in the literature, several assumptions have been taken in order to distinguish between the known and the novel emerging classes. The most recurrent one is the assumption of cohesion and separation. In other

Figure 3: Example of cluster based streaming novelty detection. In this case, more than one cluster represents a class. The boundary is formed by the union of the outlines of the clusters.

words, instances belonging to a novel class are supposed to be far away from other classes in the feature space. Also, these instances must be close from each other to consider them as a new class. In order to distinguish between novel and known classes, Euclidean distance, spherical clusters and silhouette coefficient techniques have been used in the literature [14, 20]. However, this techniques rely on strong assumptions that may not be flexible enough in some real world applications. For instance, [14, 20] need to calculate the distances to each centroid of the k-means clustering to determine whether the instance belong to that class or not. This calculation is made every time an instance needs to be classified which makes the algorithm computationally expensive. Also, in order to discover new classes, a slightly modified version of the silhouette coefficient is calculated. The use of this technique imposes that the instances of that classes need to be compact and at the same time, far from other classes. However, the proposed technique is a more general approach. Firstly, it is based on the idea that if the given data at the offline phase follows a certain probability distribution, the newcomer classes then will follow the same probability family with different parameters. This assumption makes the learning scenario more flexible in terms of shape and overlap of the classes. Secondly, the proposed method is build over a strong mathematical background which gives robustness to the algorithm.

3 Formalization of the problem

The streaming novelty detection problem can be divided in three main stages, the *offline* and *online phases* and the *update process*.

In a supervised classification problem, the objective is to learn a model \mathcal{M} that predicts the value of the target variable $c \in \mathbb{N}^1$ given a set of input features $X \in \mathbb{R}^d$ ($\mathcal{M} : X \rightarrow c$). The data is assumed to be set of pairs $\{(\mathbf{x}_1, c_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, c_n)\}$ that are generated by a generative mechanism \mathcal{G} which follows an underlying probability distribution $p(X, C)$.

In the *offline phase* denoted as time $t = 0$ for simplicity, the initial model is built $\mathcal{M}_0 : X_0 \rightarrow C_0$ by means of probability distribution $\hat{p}_0(X|C)$. In order to learn the model, a supervised set of observations $S_0 = \{(\mathbf{x}_1, c_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, c_n)\}$ are provided. This set is known as training set. The learned probability distribution p_0 can be expressed as a mixture of probability distributions of the same family with the following probability density function (pdf):

$$f_0(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^{|C_0|} p_0^j f_0^j(\mathbf{x}|c^j; \boldsymbol{\theta}_0^j) \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ represents the hyperparameters of the j^{th} mixture component at time $t = 0$, and p_0^j is the prior of the mixture component j . In the *online phase*, a sequence of unsupervised instances arrive, one instance at a time, and not necessarily in equally spaced time intervals. For each instance \mathbf{x} , a prediction is made by assigning the $\hat{c} = \arg \max_c P(c|\mathbf{x})$. If the $P(c|\mathbf{x})$ is lower than a threshold, the instance is stored in a buffer. It must be considered that at certain time $t = i + 1$, $p_{i+1}(X, C) \neq p_i(X, C)$ due to the following possible events:

- **Virtual concept drift.** The number of class labels does not change: $|C_{i+1}| = |C_i|$. However, $\exists j \in \{1, \dots, |C_i|\}$ that $f_{i+1}^j(\mathbf{x}) \neq f_i^j(\mathbf{x})$
- **Real concept drift.** The number of class labels does not change, but the hyperparameters of the mixtures do: $|C_{i+1}| = |C_i| \wedge \boldsymbol{\theta}_{i+1}^j \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}_i^j$. Hence, $p_{i+1}(c) \neq p_i(c)$.
- **Novelty.** The number of class labels changes: $|C_{i+1}| \neq |C_i|$. This can be divided in the increase or decrease of the number of class labels:
 - Increase of the number of class labels: $|C_{i+1}| > |C_i|$
 - Decrease of the number of class labels: $|C_{i+1}| < |C_i|$

Note that both events can occur at the same time i . In this sense, the number of classes would remain equal from i to $i + 1$, this change could be considered as an abrupt virtual concept drift.

- **Novelty without concept drift.** An increase or decrease of class labels occurs. Hence, $f_{i+1}(\mathbf{x}|c_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^{|c_i|} \rho_{i+1}^j(c) f_{i+1}^j(\mathbf{x}|c^j, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{i+1}^j)$. However, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i+1}^j = \boldsymbol{\theta}_i^j \forall i = 1, \dots, |C_i|$.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the offline phase of the proposed parametric framework. A model is learned from a labeled dataset.

Figure 5: Flowchart of the online phase of the proposed parametric framework. A stream of instances arrive, and for each instance a label is predicted. If the instance is predicted as novel, it is sent to the buffer. Otherwise, the instance, the prediction and the model are used to update the model for the next iteration.

- **Novelty with concept drift.** An increase or decrease of class labels occurs and also, the existing classes drift. $f_{i+1}^j(\mathbf{x}) \neq f_i^j(\mathbf{x})$ because $\exists i = 1, \dots, |C_i|$ that $\theta_{i+1}^j \neq \theta_i^j$.

The update process considers these possible events and keeps the model updated.

4 Proposed Method

The proposed framework is divided in three phases: *offline* and *online phases*, and the model *update process*. This process is generally described in Figures 4, 5 and 6 respectively.

In the *offline phase*, given a labeled dataset (training data), an initial model is learned M_0 . For each class of the training data, a probability distribution $p(X|C)$ is learned.

In the *online phase*, instances will arrive one by one in a stream fashion. For each instance \mathbf{x} , the model will predict its label \hat{c} as $\text{argmax}_c p_i(c|\mathbf{x}_i) \leq q$.

Figure 6: Flowchart of the update process in the online phase of the proposed parametric framework. Given the vector of predictions, the buffered instances and the current model, the update process outputs the new updated model and the predictions for the buffered instances.

Where q stands for a user defined density threshold. This threshold controls the ease with which an instance is considered a novelty pattern candidate. If it is considered a novelty pattern, the instance will be kept on a buffer of fixed size. The *offline phase* is divided into epochs. Each epoch consists on the interval between every filled buffer. Every epoch contains the information about the previous state to the discovering task.

The purpose of the *update process* is twofold. On the one hand, for every instance classified as a known class (not as novelty pattern), it updates the current model (see Figure 5). In order to do that, the pair (\mathbf{x}, \hat{c}) is used. On the other hand, when the number of instances in the buffer reaches its maximum capacity, the discovering task is run by the update process in order to discover new emerging classes. At this point, new classes can be discovered, by means of learning a new mixture component from the buffered instances. At the same time, the parameters of the existing mixture model can change. This can happen due to the fact that some instances could have been accidentally stored in the buffer. In order to do this learning task, it must be a balance between the importance of the buffered instances (new data) and the mixture model (which represents the old data). The discovering task then uses the information gathered from the last epoch. In this way, a Markovian approach is considered.

As the reader might have realized already, how the information of the previous models is added in the discovering task is crucial. In the literature, [4] called this as forgetting mechanism. There is an important question that must be addressed: Which should be the importance of the current model with respect to the buffered instances? This question could be considered easy to answer but different scenarios can occur.

On the one hand, whenever a new class appears, the discovering task can think that it is not a new class but an extension of a already known one. This

situation happens when the importance of the old models is too low with respect to the buffered instances. On the other hand, the discovering task can discover a new class while at the same time, minimizes the variances of the known mixture components. In a distribution learning scenario, the known models are represented by the hyperparameters of the mixture model. Then, balancing this information in a learning process in which both probability distributions and data points are available is a challenging task. During this work, some approaches have been tested to solve this problem. Firstly, sampling the mixture components individually was considered. However, if it is assumed that in this scenario there are memory limitations and the original instances can not be stored, sampling the same or some instances would not be appropriate. Furthermore, sampling some probability distribution families is not a trivial task. Secondly, having a user defined, constant decay factor has also been considered. In this way, the hyperparameters of the mixture that are introduced in the learning method are weighted. Nevertheless, the weights did only work in some situations. In others, the new classes were not discovered or the variance of the existing classes were minimized. In this way, we realized that the weight varies on each epoch. Therefore, an exponential function that used the following features extracted from the epoch was used. The number of instances classified as each existing class, the number of iterations of the epoch and the buffer size. An exponential function was built with unfruitful results. Although the performance of the discovering process increased dramatically, there were some situations in which the same problems occur. Hence, the features that were used in this task were rather uninformative or, the design of the exponential function was not sufficient to properly balance the mixture model with respect to the buffered instances. Therefore, a meta-regression approach has been adopted in this paper that overcomes the aforementioned issues. The regressor is learned using as much information as available in the epoch which is listed as follows:

- The number of instances that have been classified as each known class during the last epoch.
- The entropy of the mixture model at the time that the discovering task is run. The entropy [1] is calculated as

$$Ent(\mathcal{M}_t) = - \sum_{j=1}^{|C|} \sum_{i=1}^n t_{ij}(\hat{\theta}_j) \log t_{ij}(\hat{\theta}_j) \quad (2)$$

where

$$t_{ij}(\hat{\theta}_j) = \frac{p_k f(\mathbf{x}_i | j_k)}{\sum_{h=1}^{|C|} p_h f(\mathbf{x}_i | c_h)} \quad (3)$$

- Mean and variance of the time that takes to predict an instance of every class. In other words, the mean and variance of the time passes between the prediction of an instance as class c and the next one classified as same class c .

- The mean and variance of the densities that each mixture component assigns to the instances of the buffer.

The intuition behind these features is to model the location of the classes and the instances in the feature space, the arrival rate of instances and its quantity; and the overlap of the existing classes in the feature space. Note that the regressor must output as many weights as known models exist at the time that the discovering task is run. Furthermore, there is a tight correlation among the output variables. Therefore, on the one hand, the regression model must be a multioutput regression model, and on the other hand, a meta-regressor that considers as many regression models as mixture components exists is necessary.

It has been empirically tested that the values that the regressor outputs when a concept drift case occur are widely different than when a novel class has emerge. Consequently, a two step approach has been adopted. Firstly, a random forest classifier predicts one of both situations and secondly, depending on the output one of the two regression model is used to predict the weights.

These regression models have been trained by randomly generating learning scenarios that are explained in the supplementary material of this paper. The goal is to expose the regressor to as many situations as possible in a random way, with different overlap between new and existing classes and different arrival rates.

4.1 Illustration with the Gaussian distribution

The proposed framework has been generally described and any distribution family can be used. In order to perform a comprehensive experimental study, the Gaussian distribution family is adopted to illustrate the proposed framework. The pseudocode is shown in Algorithms 1, 3 and ??.

In order to fulfill all the requirements of the proposed probabilistic framework, the following concrete specifications have been considered that strictly derive from the selected Gaussian distribution family. Regarding the *offline phase*, the model is a Gaussian mixture model in which each individual class consist on a Gaussian distribution. According to the *online phase*, to predict new instances, instead of evaluating the density of the instances and then, reject or accept them using a threshold, the Mahalanobis distance from an instance to each distribution is computed. Then, a threshold is used to predict the instance as novelty pattern candidate and store it in a buffer. If the instance is not considered as novelty, the class of the closest distribution is assigned. The threshold is based on the percentage of probability mass of the Gaussian. Formally, the squared Mahalanobis distance has the following form:

$$d_M^2(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\mu}; G(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \Sigma)) = (\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu}) \quad (4)$$

and if $\forall c \in C$, $d_M^2(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\mu}; G_c(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \Sigma))$ is less than $\chi_{d,1-\alpha}^2$, where d stands for the number of dimensions and α the user defined percentage, the instance is labeled as novelty pattern candidate.

In the discovering task, the Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm is used to learn new classes. The number of classes is determined by minimizing the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) over a set of clustering results. As has been mentioned before, the discovering task must consider the importance of the known models with respect to the buffered instances. This importance is predicted using a meta-regression model. It has been empirically tested that having a random forest classifier that filters between an extension of the existing classes, and a new class scenario; and different regression models for each case, highly improves the accuracy of this technique. Then the prediction is made as follows. Firstly, a classifier predicts if the buffered instances are an extension of the existing ones, or if they constitute a new class (see Figure 7). Secondly, depending on the result of the previous classification model, the corresponding regression model is used to predict the importance of the known models with respect to the buffered instances. The classifier is a random Forest and the regression models are a 3-NN regression models. This models are already trained and given. The features that these regression and classification models use are the following:

- Number of instances of each class. This feature gives the information about the presence or absence of any class.
- The entropy of the model. With this feature, the disorder of the feature space can be guessed.
- The parameters of the known models. This features represent the distribution of the models in the feature space.
- The mean and variance of time between instances that are classified as same class. With this feature, the tendency of the arrival rate of each class can be guessed. For instance, if a class is gradually disappearing can be guessed with this feature.

Algorithm 1: Offline phase

Input : DS= $\{(\mathbf{x}_1, c_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_n, c_n)\}$
classifierNDorCD,
regressionModelNovelty,
regressionModelCD

Output :

$$\mathcal{M}_t = p_0(X|C_0) = \sum_{j=1}^{|C_0|} G_j(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \Sigma)$$

5 Experiments

This section describes the experiments carried out for this study and analyzes the experimental results. In these experiments, the proposed framework is compared

(a) Extension of the current models.

(b) Detection of a new class.

Figure 7: Two different situations that the update process can face during the discovering of new classes.

Algorithm 2: Online phase

Input : $\mathcal{M}_t = p_t(X|C_t) = \sum_{j=1}^{|C_t|} G_j(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$,
 \mathbf{x}_i ,
maxBufferSize,
buffer,
preds

Output :

for $c \in C$ **do**
 $\mathbf{d} = \text{mahalanobisDist}(\mathbf{x}_i, G_c)$
if $\mathbf{d} \geq \chi_{d,1-\alpha}^2$ **then**
 buffer = buffer \cup \mathbf{x}_i
 if |buffer| \geq maxBufferSize **then**
 preds[preds == -1] = updatePhase(buffer, preds, \mathcal{M}_t)
 else
 newLabel = -1
 preds = preds \cup newLabel
else
 newLabel = $\arg \min_c \mathbf{d}$
 preds = preds \cup newLabel

Algorithm 3: Update phase

Input : $\mathcal{M}_t = p_t(X|C_t) = \sum_{j=1}^{|C_t|} G_j(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \Sigma)$,
classifierNDorCD,
regressionModelNovelty,
regressionModelCD,
buffer,
preds

Output :
features = extractFeatures(preds, buffer, \mathcal{M}_t)
isConceptDriftOrNovelty = classifierNDorCD(features)
if *isConceptDriftOrNovelty* **then**
 # Novelty
 weightKnownModels = regressionModelNovelty(features)
else
 # Concept Drift
 weightKnownModels = regressionModelCD(features)
 \mathcal{M}_{t+1} , preds = emAlgorithm(buffer, \mathcal{M}_t , weightKnownModels)
return \mathcal{M}_{t+1} , *preds*

with two state of the art techniques such as MINAS [4] and SENCForest [17]. The experiments have been run using public datasets from the UCI repository. Moreover, the synthetic dataset used in [17] has also been used to compare these algorithms. A brief description of the datasets is exposed in Table 1.

In order to test a variety of possible real world situations, and have a fine control over a set of different features such as the moment in which the new classes emerge. The number of new emerging classes that emerge at the same time. The rate in which these new classes arrive, as well as the rate in which the classes disappear. The overlap between the newcomer classes and the existing ones. And finally, the shape of the classes. 5 different synthetic datasets have been created, along with 6 different strategies. Figure 8 shows the different scenarios that are used for 3 classes. The experiments with 2 and 4 classes can be found in the supplementary material. Regarding the 3 class dataset, 2 of them are supplied at the offline phase to learn the initial model, and one is discovered throughout the stream. In Figure 9, the strategies in which how the classes emerge and disappear is modelled. Note that the first 7000 iterations are only showed in these strategies. The following iterations the curves remain constant, without variation, until the user ends the test. This situation is also interesting since it is a period of stability in which the algorithm is tested. In all the datasets, 5000 instances of each training class are given to learn the initial model.

In order to compare the proposed algorithm with the state of the art approaches, some variations have been done. For instance, the SENC Forest algorithm classifies any new emerging class with the same label. In this way, the

Figure 8: Synthetic scenarios for 3 classes. 2 classes are given at the offline phase (black and red) and one (green) is discovered throughout the stream.

Table 1: Brief description of used state of the art datasets.

Dataset	# Attributes	# Examples	# Classes	Training Classes
KDDCup 99 [†]	34	4854885	4	1, 10
Cover Forest	10	551443	4: [1,2,3,7]	1, 2
SENC Forest	2	16000	4: [1, 2, 3, 4]	1, 2

global error can not be measured since there is no missclassification among the new emerging classes. Besides, the MINAS technique tries to maximize the global accuracy among the new discovered classes by reordering them. This is done due to the relabelling problem [5]. In the proposed algorithm, the predictions are reordered in order to minimize the prediction error.

The parameters of the two state of the art algorithms are exposed in Table 2. This parameters have been taken from the original papers according to their best results and the comparative study. Regarding the proposed algorithm, the percentile is fixed to 98%, the maximum number of new classes to appear at a time is set to 2 and the buffer size is set to 500 instances.

5.1 Model Evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance of the classifiers in streaming novelty detection, classical techniques from supervised classification are not representative enough in this streaming environment. Therefore, many researchers have proposed alternative evaluation measures to deal with this learning scenario. For instance, [14] proposed the percentage of misclassified instances belonging to a

Figure 9: Arrival strategies for 3 classes. With these strategies the arrival and disappearance of the classes are controlled.

Table 2: Parameters of the state of the art algorithms used in the experiments.

Algorithms	Parameters	Settings
SENC Forest	Subsample size	100
	Number of trees	100
MINAS	Buffer Size	2000
	Minimum number of examples in the cluster	20
	k = Number of micro-clusters	100
	Window size to forget outdated data	10000 / k
	Threshold	2.0
	Clustering algorithm	clustream

Table 3: Summary of the state of the art evaluation measures.

Measure	Calculation
EN_Accuracy	$\frac{A_n + A_0}{\# \text{ Instances}}$
F-measure	$\frac{2 * P * R}{P + R}$
Miss New	$\frac{\# \text{ Instances from a new class classified among OLD class}}{\# \text{ NEW instances}}$
False New	$\frac{\# \text{ Instances from an OLD class classified as NEW}}{\# \text{ OLD instances}}$
Global Error	$\frac{\# \text{ Incorrect classified instances}}{\# \text{ Instances}}$
Correct Between Known	$\frac{\# \text{ Correct classified among known classes at that epoch}}{\# \text{ instances from known classes at that epoch}}$

A_n : # emerging class instances identified as new class.
 A_0 : # known class instances classified as known.
 P : Precision of the emerging class.
 R : Recall of the emerging class.

new class which have been classified as an old class (Miss new), the percentage of misclassified instances from an old class which have been classified as a new class (False new), the classification accuracy among known classes, the global classification accuracy and the global error. Similarly, in [22] the average precision among all classes is used. In [17] the EN_accuracy and F-measure is used. This measures are summarized in Table 3.

In this paper, the global error and the EN_Accuracy measures are used to illustrate the behavior of the classifiers. However, the aforementioned evaluation measures can be found in the supplementary material of this paper. All the evaluation measures have been computed every 500 iterations in an accumulative manner throughout the stream.

5.2 SENC Forest dataset

This dataset is a synthetic dataset composed by 4 Gaussian distributions. It only has 2 dimensions and the Gaussians are partially overlapped as can be seen in Figure 10. In Table 1 a summary of this dataset can be found. In the offline phase 2 classes are supplied to learn the model. Concretely, 2000 instances of each class are given. In the online phase, instances from all classes are supplied for prediction. First, instances for the first class are given. Next, for the second class and so on until the stream is complete. In this way, the reactivity of the classifier against a new emerging class can be seen.

5.3 Cover Forest dataset

This is a public dataset which can be gathered from de UCI repository ¹. It is composed by cartographic variables of two American forests. Each instance corresponds to a 30×30 meters cell. In this dataset, the objective is to predict the cover forest specie type of each instance. In order to compare the proposed

¹<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/covertypes>

Figure 10: Plot of the SENC Forest Dataset.

framework with the other literature techniques, the same modifications that other algorithms proposed in their papers have been carried out [4, 17]. In this way, in the cover forest dataset all the binary attributes have been removed and hence, only 10 variables are considered. In Table 1 a summary of this dataset is exposed.

5.4 KDD Cup 99'

This is a publicly available dataset ² used in the third international Knowledge Discovery and Data mining tools competition. The goal was to make a classifier capable of distinguishing between legitimate and illegitimate connections in a computer network.

In order to compare the results with other techniques, the same modifications that have been made in the other works have been carried out. In this way, only the four largest classes of the KDDCup dataset are used in the experiments, i.e., *normal*, *neptune*, *smurf* and *back*. In Table 1 a summary of this dataset can be found.

5.5 Proposed synthetic scenarios

In order to properly evaluate different aspects in a controlled manner, 5 scenarios have been created. These scenarios consist in a 2 dimensional datasets (see Figure 8). Also, 6 different strategies have been created to consider different arrival rates of each class (see Figure 9).

²<http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>

Figure 11: Stream captures of the proposed technique in one synthetic dataset. Both strategy and the scenario are the first shown in Figure 9. The first green and the red classes are supplied in the offline phase and the blue one is discovered. The points coloured in black are the buffered instances.

In the offline phase 5000 instances are supplied from each class. Then during the stream, instances will arrive according to the selected strategy. This framework can be online tested in the following website: [_____](#). In that website, each iteration of the stream is output and the feature space dynamically changes according to the class events. In this paper only the figures of merit are exposed due to the graphical limitations.

In Figure 11 the stream is shown. As can be seen, at the beginning of the stream two classes are available. Then the new class candidates, the buffered instances, arrive and the model correctly classifies them as novelty pattern candidates. Then, when the buffer is full, the discovering task discovers the new class and the predictions of these buffered instances are output. At the same time, the known models change their parameters and in this way, the concept drift is modelled. Regarding the classification error that is exposed in Figure 12, it can be said that an increasing trend is clearly shown. This happens due to the fact of absence of ground truth throughout the stream.

6 Conclusions

In this paper a general probabilistic framework to deal with streaming novelty detection has been proposed. With it, not only a general probabilistic framework is proposed but a parametric approach. This technique overcomes the state of the art issues and gives a more flexible tool based on robust mathematical background. Moreover, when the data fulfills a certain probabilistic family, this

Figure 12: Global error of the proposed approach over the synthetic dataset. Both strategy and the scenario are the first shown in Figure 9.

framework outperforms the state of the art approaches, by means of reactivity and accuracy.

As part of the future work, considering other probability families to fit this general proposed framework is a good way to continue. Moreover, considering a mixture of mixture models is also another interesting approach. In other words, modelling a class with a mixture of probability distributions.

The use of a meta regression technique to weight the importance of new data (buffered instances) with respect to the old data (known mixture model) also is a novel approach with respect to state of the art streaming literature. Furthermore, the experimental study pursued in this work covers many situations that other papers of the literature did not consider.

Besides, there is a need in the community to establish robust evaluation techniques to properly evaluate this learning scenario and to set basis in order to compare the proposed algorithms.

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